

TANGENT

REPORT ON THE DETECTION AND IMPACT ANALYSIS OF TRAFFIC EVENTS

D4.4

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 955273

Deliverable administrative information

Deliverable number	D4.4
Deliverable title	Report on the detection and impact analysis of traffic events
Dissemination level	Public
Submission deadline	31/10/2023
Version number	1.0
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Executive summary

The main goal of work package (WP) 4 is to develop a framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting under various circumstances (e.g., large/sport event, roadworks, accidents, etc.) while incorporating novel traffic sensing technologies from smart infrastructure and sensors. It will extend the state-of-the-art regarding traffic forecasting approaches with a focus on modern and future mobility.

The objective of this document is to introduce the anomaly detection methods and duration models that are used in the case studies of the TANGENT project to detect and analyse the impact of various events which are extreme traffic conditions caused by, e.g., an accident or nonrecurrent congestion. Survival models are developed to determine the duration of the event.

The main outcomes of Deliverable 4.4 are:

1. Description of anomaly detection algorithm, which requires a brief description of the supply forecasting models, that will be outlined in more detail in Deliverable 4.2 “Overview of the developed traffic supply forecasting approaches with benchmarks”. Furthermore, the application of the algorithm is shown for the case studies of Greater Manchester and Athens.
2. Description of the developed duration estimation method, wherefore explanatory independent variables are included. Similarly, the application of the algorithm is shown for the case studies of Greater Manchester and Athens.

The extension and completion of the models will be performed in the framework as described in Deliverable 4.5 “Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting”, which will be integrated in the TANGENT service “Service 2 - Real-Time Traffic Management Services”. Besides Greater Manchester and Athens, the case studies of Rennes and Lisbon will follow the same algorithms for anomaly detection once the supply forecasting models are applied.

Key words

Traffic supply predictions, detection of nonrecurrent congestion and incidents and its duration, survival analysis

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

Traffic congestion, as Stopher (2004) suggests, is defined as the phenomenon during which, the incoming flow of vehicles in a transportation infrastructure overcomes its traffic capacity. There are two types of traffic congestion: recurring and non-recurring. Recurring congestion emerges in periods when demand reaches a peak or in oddly shaped infrastructures, such as traffic “bottlenecks” (Kumar & Raubal, 2021). Non-recurring congestion happens in case of unexpected events, some examples of which are extreme weather conditions or road accidents (McGroarty, 2010).

Traffic congestion has massive effects on society. Firstly, travel times become unstable due to the probability of them being false as traffic can unexpectedly get stopped. Moreover, the constant speed fluctuation results in larger gas emissions than in free flow conditions (Fafoutellis et al., 2020). There are methods of predicting traffic values such as traffic flow, speed, or occupancy, based on their short-term or long-term timeseries and the use of machine learning.

The purpose of this report is the development of an anomaly detection algorithm to detect non-recurring congestion and a duration estimation method of traffic congestion incidents in urban traffic networks with the use of historical traffic data.

1.1 Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

This deliverable aims to investigate the usage of traffic supply prediction models for detecting different events and analysing their impacts' duration. The anomaly detection is performed through the use of supply forecasting models, and the determination of anomaly scores, while the impact analysis is described through duration modeling.

The proposed framework will be applied to the TANGENT use cases, as specified in Deliverable 7.1 "Definition of the Case Studies, testing methodology and stakeholders' and users' engagement campaign" and Deliverable 7.2 "System deployment and testing specifications". The results of the developed methods are described in this report for the case studies of Greater Manchester and Athens. The results will be integrated in the framework developed in Deliverable 4.5 “Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting” and hence in the traffic management support tool developed in WP6.

1.2 Intended audience

This deliverable is mainly intended to the public interested in methods for anomaly detection and duration modeling that are applicable in urban environments.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable and links with other work packages/deliverables

The remainder of this report is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of anomaly detection and duration models by defining subtasks. Furthermore, a literature review is included in this section. The anomaly detection algorithm is described in Section 3, while the duration modelling is incorporated in Section 4. Section 5 contains the link to overall framework, and how it will be applied in the traffic management support tool within the TANGENT project. Section 6 concludes the report.

This deliverable is related to the following completed deliverables:

- Deliverable 4.1 “Report on the relevant state-of-the-art approaches for traffic predictions and simulations”
- Deliverable 4.5 “Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting”
- Deliverable 7.1 “Definition of the Case Studies, testing methodology and stakeholders' and users' engagement campaign”
- Deliverable 7.2 “System deployment and testing specifications”

This deliverable is the main outcome of Task 4.4 “Identification of critical conditions and congestion duration prediction”.

2 Overview of anomaly detection and duration models

The problem of anomaly detection and duration modelling consists of two steps, namely event detection and event duration modeling. These are described briefly below, while Section 3 and 4 contain an extended description of the suggested methods. To give a complete overview, a literature review is included.

Step 1: Event detection

This step detects and foresees extreme traffic conditions (congestion) caused by, e.g., a road accident or non-recurring high traffic volumes. Nonrecurrent anomalies refer to infrequent or deviations from the norm that do not follow a predictable pattern. non-recurring congestion gets detected by comparing the current traffic state with the traffic supply predictions. When the measurements related to the current traffic state deviate too much from the predicted values, the model detects an anomaly. This step uses the developed approaches for traffic supply predictions in task 4.2, which will be outlined in detail in Deliverable 4.2 “Overview of the developed traffic supply forecasting approaches with benchmarks”. The first step is training the supply forecasting model, and applying it on the traffic values, e.g. traffic speed of the case study. Next, anomaly scores are calculated, namely statistical measurements for each location and timestamp. Based on a threshold the anomalies are detected through unsupervised machine learning models, as described in the following section. Both supervised and unsupervised methods have their place in anomaly detection, depending on the datasets and tasks at hand.

In machine learning, the key difference between supervised and unsupervised methods is that the former requires labeled data, where the desired output is known, while the latter operates on unlabeled data, discovering hidden patterns without specific guidance. Even though both supervised and unsupervised methods are applicable for detecting anomalies, the following sections will show that in this report was opted to use unsupervised methods as the labeled anomaly datasets are not available for all case studies. Another reason for the use of unsupervised models is the sparsity of the anomalies. This makes it hard to train a supervised model on them. For training a supervised model, one has to inject anomalies into the dataset, and by doing that, we are going to have to model the effect of the injected anomalies on the neighboring measurement points. That will also add redundant complexity to the framework which results in the lower quality dataset since we are moving away from the real-world dataset (Wilmet et al., 2021). The other problem that anomaly injection introduces is that since the model is going to see a lot more anomalies that happen in the real world, the false positive rate of the model is also going to increase. For these reasons, we opted for unsupervised models.

Some unsupervised methods are One-Class Support Vector Machines (Schölkopf et al., 2001), Local Outlier Factor (Breunig et al., 2000), k-nearest Neighbors (Hautamäki et al., 2004), DBSCAN (Celik et al., 2011), and isolation forest (F. T. Liu et al., 2008).

- One-Class-Support Vector Machines is an extension of Support Vector Machines that is modified to work on datasets where only one class (here, normal instances) is present during the training. This algorithm works by finding a boundary separating the normal data points from the origin, and then the points outside of this boundary are labeled as anomalies. This is one of the most accurate algorithms for the task. However, One-Class-Support Vector Machines is computationally expensive, especially for datasets as used within the TANGENT project (traffic data in urban environments), where it is normal to have tens or hundreds of thousands of instances. This method is less suitable for large datasets and real-time applications.

- Local Outlier Factor calculates the local deviation of a data point with respect to its neighbors. It then classifies those with significantly lower density than their neighbors as outliers. While Local Outlier Factor can work well for datasets with clusters of varying densities, it may struggle with high dimensional data since distance metrics can become less meaningful in such spaces, and we are extracting as many as possible from anomaly scores from the forecasting model.
- In the context of anomaly detection, k-Nearest Neighbors can be used to find the distances to the k nearest neighbors, and if the distance is above a certain threshold, the data point is considered to be an anomaly. However, k-Nearest Neighbors can be slow in real-time applications due to the need to compute distances for every query point. Also, it usually has lower accuracy than the isolation forest
- A clustering algorithm that groups together closely packed points and labels points in low-density regions as outliers is DBSCAN. The main disadvantage of DBSCAN is that it assumes clusters are of similar densities, which is not always the case. Additionally, its accuracy degrades with higher dimensions.
- Isolation Forest works on the principle that anomalies are data points that are few and are different from the rest, making them easier to isolate from the rest. It builds an ensemble of trees for the dataset, and the anomalies require fewer splits to isolate compared to normal data points.

Step 2: Event duration modeling

This step models the duration of extreme conditions due to unexpected events and/or heavy traffic. It uses input from step 1 about the events and models their evolution over the next minutes using duration modelling techniques.

Duration prediction is a widely known subject of research. Duration models are used particularly in medical studies, but their use has expanded. The most well-known duration method is Survival Analysis. An example of duration prediction using Survival Analysis is the study conducted in Texas, U.S.A. for the time between the Harvey hurricane occurred in 2007, and the time a local business reopened after that. By including independent variables such as the age of the business, its size or the percentage of damage, duration models were developed (Lee, 2021).

Survival models have also been used on the transportation sector and most frequently in road safety. Some examples of conducted researches in duration prediction using Survival Analysis are the time a patient can survive after a road accident (Ibay et al., 2019), the duration of road accidents (Huajing et al., 2022), the time it takes for traffic flow to return at its normal conditions after an accident (Kalair & Connaughton, 2021), the reaction time from user to user (Parmet et al., 2014) and the time it takes for a user to get involved in a road accident from the time he got his drivers' license (Oralhan, 2018).

Another major subject of research is the duration of parking searching. Especially in Athens, where parking space is quite limited, searching for parking can take more than 30 minutes in some densely populated areas. In recent research, using route data, the influence of factors such as land use, peak hour and day of the week was investigated (Mantouka et al., 2021).

As for traffic congestion duration, (Y. Liu et al., 2020) analyzed the routes of ten thousand vehicles and included them in a non-parametric survival model. Lastly, (Hu et al., 2019) investigated the relationship between traffic volume and speed and the distribution of congestion duration based on data collected from the city of Shenzhen in China, taking into account that the most important duration characteristic are peak hours.

3 Anomaly detection

This section describes how anomalies can be detected using data-driven approaches. Therefore, the problem is subdivided into 4 steps:

1. Train supply forecasting model
2. Apply forecasting model
3. Calculate anomaly scores
4. Detect anomalies

The supply forecasting model is used to predict the normal traffic patterns. By using insight gained by the predictions, anomalies can be detected. By comparing them with the observed values, anomaly scores are calculated. These are indicators of how the observed traffic values deviate from the predicted values. The 4 steps are outlined in the following subsections.

3.1 Train supply forecasting model

In order to determine whether an anomaly detection can be found in traffic, the predicted traffic situation at a certain place and time is compared with the actual traffic state. Therefore, the first step in detecting anomalies is the training of a supply forecasting model to obtain predicted traffic states.

Supply forecasting has been tackled from different modeling perspectives during the last years. With the rise of data collection and computational resources, data-driven approaches are used to predict the traffic state. The state-of-the-art models in deep learning traffic forecasting methods are composed of Graph Neural Networks, Recurrent Neural Networks, Convolutional Neural Networks, and Attention Mechanisms, as described in Deliverable 4.1 “Report on the relevant state-of-the-art approaches for traffic predictions and simulations”.

This implemented method for traffic supply forecasting is described in Figure 1. The steps for the supply forecasting process are described below:

1. Collection of historical and real-time traffic data. Historical data (e.g., time series of flows, speeds) coming from available traffic counters, floating vehicle data, etc., should preferably represent one year worth of data to incorporate all seasonal effects and is used for the training of the deep learning model. Real-time data, with a similar format, is used to provide traffic supply predictions in real-time based on the trained model.
2. Optional collection of external features that influence traffic (e.g., weather data, road information like road type, number of lanes.) to be combined with historical and real-time traffic data. Note that the input of weather data should be the same granularity as the traffic data itself. Furthermore, it is required to have it historically, in real-time, and a weather prediction as well.
3. Deep learning modelling (forecasting model) that performs on these type of input data.

The output of these models are time series predictions for traffic speed, traffic count, flow, occupancy, etc. for the future time steps.

Figure 1: Implemented solution for traffic supply forecasting.

Training a supply forecasting model via data-driven approaches requires historical traffic data. The historical observations are used to learn to predict future traffic conditions. Forecasting models can consider the normal traffic conditions during working days, weekends, and holidays (given enough historical data to train on all these conditions). They also predict the conditions of the morning and evening rush hours. Furthermore, they propagate the effect of anomalies that already happened in the neighboring points of measurement.

70% of the historical data is used to train the deep learning model, 10% is used for validation, and 20% for testing purposes. Validation data helps in fine-tuning the model and prevents overfitting while testing data assesses its performance on previously unseen data and ensures its generalizability.

To use the model in real-time, the past traffic conditions up to the specified input window size (16, 12, 8, or any number used during training) are required. The model outputs the specified output window size (12, 8 or any number used during training) for each location with measurements (e.g. loop detectors, routes). This is depicted in Figure 2. We further explain the architecture of the model and more technical details about them in Deliverable 4.2 “Overview of the developed traffic supply forecasting approaches with benchmarks”, due in December 2023.

Figure 2: Input and output of supply forecasting model, given the specified window sizes

3.2 Apply supply forecasting model

After training the supply forecasting model, it is applied on the last 20% of historical data to calculate anomaly scores (see Section 3.3). When applying the supply forecasting model, a sliding window approach is employed on the selected data with the stride of 1 to go through all the timestamps available in this part of the dataset. For each time series, the following statistics are calculated and stored.

- Expected mean error: For each measurement point, the expected mean error is defined as the average error for the entire 20% of historical data. These statistics provide a general sense of the model's accuracy for each measurement.
- Expected standard deviation error: Like the above, this metric measures the errors' dispersion or variability. A lower standard deviation suggests that the errors are close to the mean. On the other hand, a higher standard deviation indicates more variability in the prediction error for each measurement.
- Expected median Error: This metric provides the expected median value for each measurement point, which is the middle value when the errors are sorted. The median provides a sense of the central tendency of the errors, which can be useful when some outliers are skewing the mean.
- Expected maximum Error: This is the highest error value observed between the prediction and time series observations for each measurement point. It gives an idea of the worst-case prediction error and is useful for understanding extreme anomalies and system limitations.

These statistics are very useful in calculating the anomaly scores, as explained in the following section.

3.3 Anomaly scores

In this step, we calculate the following anomaly scores for each measurement point and timestamp. These are measured through different statistics, e.g., absolute error, squared error, z-scores, etc.

- Absolute error: This is the difference between the predicted value and the observed value, irrespective of the direction of the error. It gives a raw idea about the magnitude of the error.

$$\epsilon = |\text{predictions} - \text{observed values}|$$

- Squared error: This is the square of the difference between the predicted value and the actual value. It heavily penalizes larger errors.

$$\epsilon = (\text{predictions} - \text{observed values})^2$$

- Directed error: Similar to the absolute error but takes into account the direction of the error. For example in speed anomaly detection, we are only interested in anomalies where the observed speed is lower than the predicted speed. Similarly, in anomaly detection for travel time, we are only interested in anomalies where the observed travel time is higher than the predicted one.

$$\epsilon = \begin{cases} (\text{predictions} - \text{observed values}) \times (\text{predictions} > \text{observed values}) & \text{if direction} > 0 \\ (\text{predictions} - \text{observed values}) \times (\text{predictions} < \text{observed values}) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

- Deviation from the expected error: It is the difference between the actual error and the expected mean error. It shows how much the current error deviates from the average error we expect.

$$\epsilon = \text{absolute error} - \text{expected mean error}$$

- Z-Score: It shows the number of standard deviations by which the value of the error is different from the mean value. It's determining how unusual the error is.

$$\epsilon = \frac{\text{absolute error} - \text{expected mean error}}{\text{expected std error} + \text{EPSILON}}$$

- Median Z-Scores: Similar to the Z-score but uses the median error in its calculation.

$$\epsilon = \frac{\text{absolute error} - \text{expected median error}}{\text{expected std error} + \text{EPSILON}}$$

- Deviation from Max error: It shows the difference between the current error and the expected maximum error. A higher value indicates that the error is closer to the worst-case scenario.

$$\epsilon = \text{expected maximum error} - \text{absolute error}$$

- Mean Absolute Deviation Scores: It measures the variability of a univariate sample of quantitative data. It gives us an idea about the spread of errors.

$$\epsilon = |\text{absolute error} - \text{expected median error}|$$

- Percentage error: Represents the error as a percentage.

$$\epsilon = \frac{\text{absolute error}}{\text{observed values} * 100 + \text{EPSILON}}$$

- Logarithmic error: The logarithmic error provides a different way to penalize the error magnitudes compared to the linear methods. Using logarithm, the anomaly score grows slowly for larger deviations.

$$\epsilon = \log\left(\frac{\text{absolute error} + 1}{\text{observed values} + 1}\right)$$

3.4 Detecting anomalies

In the next step, isolation forest (F. T. Liu et al., 2008), (F. T. Liu et al., 2012), which is an unsupervised machine learning model, is used to aggregate all those anomaly scores into a unified anomaly score.

The algorithm works by isolating observations by randomly selecting a feature, namely an initially calculated anomaly score, and then randomly selecting a split value between the maximum and minimum values of the selected feature. This random partitioning produces shorter paths for anomalies in the dataset. Therefore, when an observation has a shorter path in the tree structure, it's more likely to be an anomaly. The unified anomaly score is calculated by the average path length of an observation across multiple trees in the forest. This unified anomaly score is compared with a specified threshold to determine whether it's considered an anomaly.

Isolation forest is chosen for this task since it's efficient for high dimensional data and provides several advantages, which are mentioned below, over the other methods that were listed in the literature review in Section 2, especially in our case where we run the supply forecasting and anomaly detection models in real-time in TANGENT service "Service 2 - Real-Time Traffic Management Services".

Therefore, the steps of isolation forest are explained in more detail below, and are visualized in Figure 3:

1. Random selection: The first step of isolation forest is randomly selecting a feature and then randomly selecting a split value between the minimum and maximum values of the selected feature. The randomness ensures that there is not an inherent bias towards any feature and split values.
2. Building trees: The process of randomly splitting is done recursively to divide the data into smaller subsets. The number splitting required to isolate a sample is the path length from the root node (yellow node in Figure 3) to the leaf node (green nodes in Figure 3). The path length is an indicator of our decision function. Anomalies require fewer random splits to be isolated, so they have shorter path lengths. The process explained above is for a single tree. The anomaly score is calculated by averaging the result over several trees (a forest).
3. Anomaly score: Once the forest is built, the anomaly score is measured. The score is a measure of how deep in the tree points are isolated. A lower score means that the instance is more likely to be an anomaly.
4. A threshold is specified to consider points that are below that threshold an anomaly.

The isolation forest algorithm has two important parameters: the number of base estimators (or trees) in the ensemble, and contamination, which sets the proportion of outliers in the data set. This affects the threshold for anomaly scoring. We use 100 trees to make our forest and start with the contamination of 5 percent, which means that 5 percent of instances are marked as outliers, which is going to be less than that since some of those anomalies are in the direction which we are not interested in, for example in traffic speed anomaly detection, we are only interested in instances where the observed traffic speed is lower than the predicted traffic speed, not the other way around.

Figure 3: Isolation forest to aggregate anomaly scores into a unified score.

The advantages of isolation forest are listed below:

1. Efficiency with high dimensionality: Unlike some other algorithms that we named in the literature review, the isolation forest works well when we have high number anomaly scores.
2. Computational speed: Isolation forest requires fewer splits to isolate anomalies, making the algorithm faster and more suitable for real-time processing, which is crucial in TANGENT service “Service 2 - Real-Time Traffic Management Services”.
3. Less sensitive to outlier contamination: Outlier contamination refers to the presence of a significant number of anomalies in a dataset that can skew or distort the underlying statistical properties and analyses. Isolation forest does not rely on distance or density measures to detect anomalies; it remains robust even when the data has many anomalies. It doesn't get misled by shifts in the perceived center or density of the data.
4. Scalability: Isolation Forest can handle large datasets, which is beneficial for applications that require large historical data for training and processing large streams of data for real-time anomaly detection.

Based on the requirements of handling huge amounts of data for training models and processing results in real-time, Isolation Forest stands out as the most suitable choice. Furthermore, by opting for an unsupervised approach, we avoid the pitfalls of manual anomaly injection and maintain the integrity and authenticity of the datasets.

3.5 Results

3.5.1 Data

In this report, two databases of traffic volume measurements from two European cities, Athens and Manchester, were considered. In Athens, the population of the city center is about 1 million inhabitants, while in the wider area it reaches almost 3 million. Meanwhile, Manchester has a population of 550 thousand inhabitants, while the Greater Manchester area has a population of over 2.8 million, making it the second most populated metropolitan area in the United Kingdom.

3.5.1.1 Athens

The data used in this study were provided to the National Technical University of Athens by the Traffic Management authority of the Region of Attica. They consist of two days of measurements (9th and 10th of November 2022) from loop detectors in the greater area of Athens. Specifically for the case of anomaly detection, traffic data was collected for two weeks in 2023; a week with normal operation of the network (February 20th – February 26th) and a week with a known (severe) flooding event (September 11th – September 17th). More specifically, the database consists of hourly traffic volume (veh/h), speed (km/h) and occupancy (%) measurements with a time resolution of 90 seconds. The locations of the detectors are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Exact location of loop detectors in Athens

3.5.1.2 Manchester

On the other hand, traffic speed and volume measurements have been made available from Manchester, with a resolution of 5 minutes and a duration of 13 months (1st January 2022 to 31st January 2023). The locations of the loop detectors are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Exact location of loop detectors in Manchester

3.5.2 Greater Manchester

In this section we show and discuss some results for anomaly detection in the Greater Manchester area. Regarding traffic speed. Utilizing the isolation forest method for detection, the results of this method are plotted on a graph (Figure 6) for the first 500 timestamps of sensor ID 1001. On this graph, blue dots represent anomalies, while red dots show normal conditions. Lower anomaly scores mean more extreme anomalies. Contrary to what you might assume first, the red points with low scores signify anomalies we are not interested in. Specifically, in these instances, the observed speed is higher than the model's predictions.

Figure 6: Anomaly scores over time for a specific sensor in Greater Manchester. Blue dots represent anomalies, while red dots show normal conditions.

Figure 7 contains samples where anomalies get detected. They are visualized via the vertical red line. Here a share decline in the observed traffic speed is detected. The following patterns emerge in these instances:

- Close Alignment: This suggests that the predictions are typically in sync with the previously observed values.
- Sharp decline: A sudden and significant drop happens in the observed values.
- Deviation from prediction: These declines stand out because they deviate considerably from the predicted values.

We consider these instances as anomalies in the system which can be the results of a non-recurrent incident like an accident.

Figure 7: Samples of a sharp decline in the observed traffic speed in the Greater Manchester area. Orange lines (cross) show the observed values, while the blue lines represent the supply predictions. An anomaly (vertical red line) is detected.

In contrast, when there’s a sharp increase in the forecasted traffic speed, different patterns can be noted:

- Sudden spikes: There are unexpected sharp spikes in the predicted traffic speed.
- Consistent Observed speeds: The actual readings from the sensors often remain consistent with the previous observations.
- Forecasting model: It is important to realize that the model not only considers the past observation of sensors for predicting the future, but it also takes into account the neighboring sensors to create more accurate predictions. The past readings from those neighbors affect the prediction significantly. By looking closer at the figures, we can see that these instances happen in the early morning, which is likely that the sensors only detect a handful of vehicles, and it’s more likely that some of those drive at an illegal speed, affecting their and neighbors’ predictions.

Samples of these sharp increases are shown in the following figure.

Figure 8: Samples of a sharp increase in the predicted traffic speed in the Greater Manchester area. Orange lines (cross) show the observed values, while the blue lines represent the supply predictions. An anomaly (vertical red line) is detected.

3.5.3 Athens

Similarly, as for Greater Manchester, some results are shown for Athens. For every sensor, a graph with anomaly scores can be constructed. Figure 9 depicts anomaly scores for the Athens case study for the different days described in the data section. Red points are anomalies, while blue points are normal scores. The contamination threshold is set at 5%. This implies that the thresholds are determined such that 5% of the data is classified as anomalous. However, certain anomalies, specifically those where the predicted traffic speed is lower than the observed traffic speed, are not of interest to our analysis. Consequently, these specific anomalies are not flagged, resulting in a final anomaly percentage that is less than the initial 5% threshold. The figure shows that the red dots only occurred during event days. As explained in the methodology, anomalies are detected by comparing the predicted with the observed traffic speed (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Anomaly scores over time for a specific sensor for the Athens case study. Red points are anomalies, which can be seen during event days (September 2023).

Figure 10: Traffic supply predictions with observed values for a specific sensor for the Athens case study. Yellow lines are anomalies.

4 Duration models

Firstly, two congestion detection methods are applied, in two cities, Athens and Manchester, with the output being the number of congestion occurrences. For the development of the congestion duration estimating models, the most suitable independent explanatory variables are chosen according to the assumption that they have impact on duration. Then, three different Survival Analysis models are applied, to examine the impact of each variable.

4.1 Methodology

To develop the congestion duration prediction models, the output of one of the detection methods is chosen and Survival Analysis is conducted by using three different survival models and inserting some independent variables. Then, the results of each model and the effect of each independent variable are discussed, and conclusions are drawn.

4.1.1 Basic concepts of Survival Analysis

In this chapter, the theory behind Survival Analysis and the models developed is presented (Washington et al., 2004). Survival Analysis got its name from the first applications of the method, as it was used in research regarding the surviving time of patients (time passed until the patient's death). The survival curve depicts the probability that the duration T of a phenomenon is greater than or equal to a timestamp t :

$$S(t) = P(T \geq t) \quad (1)$$

Where P the probability, T a random time variable and t a specific moment in time. There are also the Hazard Functions which are based on the following cumulative distribution function:

$$F(t) = P(T < t) \quad (2)$$

The corresponding density function is:

$$f(t) = \frac{dF(t)}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the hazard function is:

$$h(t) = \frac{f(t)}{[1 - F(t)]} \quad (4)$$

The following figure depicts all the functions mentioned:

Figure 11: Depiction of the basic Survival Analysis functions (Washington et al., 2004)

Based on the above, the relationships between the functions are as follows:

$$S(t) = 1 - F(t) = 1 - \int_0^t f(t)dt = EXP[-H(t)] \quad (6)$$

$$f(t) = \frac{d}{dt}F(t) = h(t)EXP[-H(t)] = -\frac{d}{dt}S(t) \quad (7)$$

$$H(t) = \int_0^t h(t)dt = -LN[S(t)] \quad (8)$$

$$h(t) = \frac{f(t)}{S(t)} = \frac{f(t)}{1 - F(t)} = \frac{d}{dt}H(t) \quad (9)$$

Additionally, explanatory variables can be inserted in the survival models. There are two ways of incorporating explanatory variables in the hazard function. The first one is the proportional model, in which it is assumed that they act multiplicatively on the baseline hazard function $h_0(t)$ and specifically the $EXP(\beta X)$ function, where β is the coefficient of the independent variable. Accordingly, the hazard function ends up as follows:

$$h(t; X) = h_0(t)EXP(\beta X) \quad (10)$$

Figure 12: Explanatory variable input in the base hazard function with the proportional model (Washington et al., 2004)

The second one is the accelerated lifetime model, in which the effect of the explanatory variable is inserted in the baseline survival function $S_0(t)$ in the form of the function of the $EXP(\beta X)$ function. The survival function of the model in question, when all explanatory variables are zero, is equal to the baseline function. The new survival function is:

$$S(t; X) = S_0[tEXP(\beta X)] \quad (11)$$

and the hazard function is:

$$h(t; X) = h_0[tEXP(\beta X)]EXP(\beta X) \quad (12)$$

Duration data can be left-censored, right-censored or none of the two. When developing a duration model between two specific moments in time t_1 and t_2 , left-censored are the durations of a phenomenon that started before the moment t_1 and right-censored are those that end after the moment t_2 . In these cases, modelling is more complicated as there is critical information missing.

4.1.2 Types of duration models

Duration models are divided into three categories: nonparametric models, semi-parametric models and fully parametric models. Nonparametric models do not use any explanatory variables and there is no assumption of a specific duration distribution. These are also the main reasons that nonparametric models are not used regularly in the transportation field. A well-known example of nonparametric models is the Kaplan-Meier method (Kaplan & Meier, 1958).

Semi-parametric models have a parametric assumption that explanatory variables influence the hazard function, but they do not assume a distribution of duration times. The most used semi-parametric model is the **Cox Proportional Hazard** (Cox, 1972) which is based on the ratio of hazards in every observation i of the phenomenon studied and has the following equation:

$$\frac{EXP(\beta X_i)}{\sum_{j \in R_i} EXP(\beta X_j)} \quad (13)$$

where R_i indicates the set of observations j .

Fully parametric models assume both a parametric influence of the explanatory variables as well as a statistical distribution of duration times, such as **Weibull** distribution. The density Weibull function is:

$$f(t) = (\lambda P)(\lambda t)^{P-1} \text{EXP}[(\lambda t)^P] \quad (14)$$

with a hazard function:

$$h(t) = (\lambda P)(\lambda t)^{P-1} \quad (15)$$

4.1.3 Model evaluation

To evaluate the correlation between two samples (real duration times and predicted duration times) a statistical test has to be conducted. Comparing the classification of the two samples is the key to measure their deviation. An indicative statistical test is that of the **Concordance index (C-index)**. C-index shows how well the prediction fits the actual data. It actually checks if predicted values have the same distribution as the actual data and if they have the same relationship between them. Its values range from 0 to 1, where values higher than 0.50 indicate a well-fitted model.

4.2 Implementation and results

The results that are described in this section start from the same datasets as the one in the previous section on anomaly detection.

4.2.1 Independent variables selection

In order to develop duration prediction models, the selection and estimation of the most relevant features is required. Based on the data availability, in this work the following variables are exploited: time of the day and whether it is during the peak hour (categorical), number of lanes and traffic volume at the beginning of the event.

4.2.1.1 Peak hour

By observing the average time series of traffic volume for both cities (Athens and Manchester) the exact peak hour periods were detected. More specifically, in Athens, two distinct peak hour periods can be observed: the morning peak, between 7 a.m. and 11 a.m. and the afternoon peak, between 2 p.m. and 7 p.m. On the other hand, in Manchester, there is a single, unified period between 10 a.m. and 6 p.m. when traffic volume is significantly increased. When an event occurs during the above periods the peak hour variable's value is 1 (or 2 for afternoon peak for Athens only); else it is 0. As it is expected, most congestion events take place during peak hour. The number of incidents according to the values of the peak hour variable are presented below in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Distribution of congestion events during peak hour

4.2.1.2 Number of lanes

The number of lanes is an additional factor that influences the duration of a congestion incident. In a one- or two-lane road section, congestion is more likely to occur than in a four-lane section of an arterial and last for longer. The independent variable of the number of lanes was only used in the development of the Athens road network model because there was no information on the number of lanes of the sections of the Manchester measurement locations. In Figure 14 the distribution of the number of congestion incidents per number of lanes is presented for the road network of Athens.

Figure 14: Distribution of congestion events per number of lanes

4.2.1.3 Traffic volume at the beginning of congestion

The traffic volume at the beginning of the incident was also passed to the model, as it is indicative of its severity.

4.2.2 Survival analysis

In this report, two well-known Survival Analysis methods were implemented: Cox model of proportional hazard and Weibull distribution. First, the actual survival curves of the detected incidents are presented in Figure 8 for each city. Although there are some obvious similarities between the two curves, one may notice that the incidents in Manchester have a longer duration in general. Indicatively, 50% of the congestion incidents in Athens last for at least 30 minutes, while in Manchester the corresponding duration is 38 minutes. The reason for this may be that the single peak hour period observed in

Manchester favors longer lasting duration; however, the corresponding incidents are less severe than those observed in Athens (e.g., higher speed compared to incidents in Athens).

Figure 15: Actual survival curves of congestion duration

4.2.3 Results of Cox model

The results of the model’s fitting are presented in Table 1 below. The concordance index equals 0.58 for Athens and 0.56 for Manchester, which is a decent value. Also, as the p-values of the variables indicate, the Traffic volume and peak hour are the most significant ones, contributing to the estimation of the duration of the events.

Variable	coefficient	z	p-value
Athens			
Number of lanes	-0.05	-1.05	0.29
Traffic volume	-0.00	-4.35	<0.005
Morning peak	-0.39	-4.16	<0.005
Afternoon peak	-0.29	-3.65	<0.005
Manchester			
Traffic volume	0.15	2.00	0.05
Peak hour	-0.00	-4.2	<0.005

Table 1: Results of Cox model

The average effect of each variable on the risk function is presented in Figure 16 below. The peak hours and the number of lanes (for Athens only) seem to have the strongest influence on the model’s output. However, as mentioned previously, the p-value of the number of lanes is relatively low to be considered as a statistically significant variable.

Figure 16: Effect of independent variables per city for Cox model

A more detailed presentation of the effect of peak hour on the duration of traffic congestion incidents is given in Figure 17. For the case of Athens, incidents that occur during peak hour obviously seem to last for longer, and especially during the morning peak. On the other hand, the opposite is true for Manchester: although a higher number of congestion events are observed during the single peak hour period, durations may be longer during off-peak periods.

Figure 17: Survival curves per peak hour for Cox model

4.2.4 Results of Weibull distribution model

The Weibull distribution survival model is a parametric model that assumes that the risk function follows the Weibull distribution. The results of its implementation are similar to Cox model and the concordance indices 0.58 and 0.56 for Athens and Manchester, respectively. In Table 2 the coefficients and significance of the independent variables are presented.

Variable	coefficient	z	p-value
Athens			
Number of lanes	0.03	1.13	0.26
Traffic volume	+0.00	4.35	<0.005
Morning peak	0.31	4.92	<0.005
Afternoon peak	0.22	4.03	<0.005
Lambda_intercept	3.4	46.30	<0.005
rho_intercept	0.40	17.07	<0.005
Manchester			
Traffic volume	+0.00	19.15	<0.005
Peak hour	-0.09	-9.59	<0.005
Lambda_intercept	3.9	344.02	<0.005
rho_intercept	0.48	98.69	<0.005

Table 2: Results of Weibull model

Correspondingly, the effects of the variables are also presented in Figure 18 and Figure 19. The outcomes are, in general, similar to those of the Cox model.

Figure 18: Effect of independent variables per city for Weibull model

Figure 19: Survival curves per peak hour for Weibull model

5 Framework & TANGENT API integration

The output of this deliverable will be used as input, through the framework described in Deliverable 4.5 “Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting”, to the TANGENT service “Service 2 - Real-Time Traffic Management Services”. In Service 2, the triggering conditions are provided by the supply forecasting and event detection and duration prediction models (Table 9 in D6.1, Incidents).

6 Conclusions

This report describes the anomaly detection algorithm and the duration estimation methods. The problem is divided into two subtasks, namely anomaly detection and duration modelling. Both focus in application on the use cases of Greater Manchester and Athens.

The anomaly detection algorithm is based on a comparison between the observed value, e.g. speed, travel time, etc., and the traffic supply prediction. The advantages of unsupervised anomaly detection methods are explained in this report. Some strengths and weaknesses of the proposed model framework were proposed through examples in the cases of Greater Manchester and Athens. The model is able to detect many sorts of anomalies and will discard some anomalies that are not in our interest. On the contrary, one of the weaknesses occurs especially in the early morning when the number of vehicle detections is very low, and someone driving at an illegal speed can alter the prediction of the corresponding location and the surrounding locations.

Two Survival Analysis models for estimating duration of congestion incidents that emerged in Athens and Manchester are proposed. In Athens there is a significantly higher number of them, but those in Manchester have a longer duration in general. The implementation of the Survival models for estimating their duration highlighted that there are some common patterns in both cities regarding the most influential variables, but also significant differences.

The methods discussed in this report will be used as input, through the framework described in Deliverable 4.5 “Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting”, to the TANGENT service “Service 2 - Real-Time Traffic Management Services”.

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